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The authors declare no competing interests.

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Conference Abstract

MUDUDI'S VIEW OF ISLAMIC ECONOMICS IN THE GLOBAL WORLD

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ABSTRACT

Islam provides a complete guideline for the economic life of an individual, a society, a nation and the whole world. Maududi in his book *First Principles of Islamic Economics* has discussed the Islamic economic system in detail. The global world marked with capitalism has led to many economic problems of interest-based economy, profit maximisation, exploitation, poverty, and many others. Islamic economic system provides solutions to the global economic issues. It is a qualitative study using content analysis as a research method. This paper provides an analysis of Maududi's book *First Principles of Islamic Economics*. Maududi's thought of Islamic Economic system and its use in the global world are highlighted in this paper. This study is worthwhile from the perspective of various fields like economics, Islamic studies, education, sociology, human resource management, business studies, and so on.

Keywords Islam, Economics, vision of Syed Maududi, Capitalism, Global

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